

Auxetic Materials for Biomimicry: Designing for Tendon-Like Behavior

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Abstract—Tendon healing is slow and rarely restores full functionality. Studies show that in the toe region, up to 2% deformation, tendons behave as auxetic materials. This work aims to optimize a 2D re-entrant auxetic cell to replicate tendon Poisson ratio and stiffness for improved biomechanical performance.

Keywords—metamaterials, auxetic materials, tendon, biomimicry.

I. INTRODUCTION

The physiological role of tendons is to transmit load from muscles to bones to permit the body movement. They are composed by a hierarchical structure of collagen fibres. The hierarchical structure of the tendon is illustrated in Fig. 1. Over 30 million tendon interventions happened every year

Fig. 1. Hierarchical structure of tendons. Image credit: [Smart Servier](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#).

worldwide [1]. Despite the increased possibility of modern medicine, it is still impossible to achieve a full restoration of the pre-injured performance of the tendon, for example the tensile strength of a healed tendon can be 30% less than the healthy one [2]. As a consequence the risk of recurrence is high and the functionality of the tendon can be reduced according to the severity of the residual damage. In 2015 Gatt et al. [3] report that tendons show an auxetic behaviour. Auxetic materials are a class of mechanical metamaterials that present a negative Poisson ratio. Under tensile loading, they expand perpendicular to the applied force, while under compressive loading, they contract laterally. This study focuses on biomimicry, a design approach inspired by natural structures

and processes. The term “biomimicry” comes from the Greek words “bios” (life) and “mimesis” (imitation), reflecting the goal of replicating efficient strategies found in nature. Tendon deformation can be divided into three phases. The first one is called the toe region (between 0-2% of deformation), in this phase the tendon shows a wave-form shape which disappears with increasing strain. *In vivo* tendons usually deform in this zone. The second phase is the strain region (between 2-6% of deformation) in this phase collagen fibres are no longer crimped and they are strained by the applied load. The third phase is associated with tendon rupture [4]. Fig. 2 provides a schematic representation of the stress-strain behaviour of tendons. Specifically, Gatt et al. demonstrate that in the toe region the Achilles tendon exhibits a negative Poisson ratio. Integrating auxeticity in the design of an artificial substitute can result in a more effective device. The primary objective of this research is to develop

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the stress-strain behavior of the tendon. Image credit: [OpenStax](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#).

and optimize a re-entrant unit cell capable of emulating the characteristic stress-strain response of tendons, particularly in the initial toe region and the subsequent linear elastic region. Achieving this goal could enable the design of bio-inspired auxetic structures that better replicate tendon mechanics and improve the performance of artificial tendon substitutes.

II. METHODS

Firstly, among all possible auxetic mechanisms, a re-entrant mechanism was selected due to its simplicity and the fact

that it is the most widely studied and characterized in the literature. Consequently, a 2D re-entrant honeycomb structure was chosen as the basis for optimization. Once the base geometry was defined, the parameters requiring optimization were identified. The study focused on three main objectives: optimizing the Poisson's ratio in the toe region, adjusting the Young's modulus in the linear strain region, and limiting the auxetic behavior to the toe region. The initial geometry was constructed starting from a "Z"-shaped configuration, which provides the characteristic re-entrant profile. The parameters considered for optimization included the length of each rib (L_1 , L_2 , L_3), the cross-sectional dimensions of each rib (height (H) and base (B) length, assuming a rectangular section), and the re-entrant angle of the cell (α). A schematic representation of the unit cell is shown in Fig. 3. These parameters were chosen because they directly influence the mechanical response, including stiffness, auxeticity, and the transition between the toe and linear strain regions.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the unit cell and the parameter which characterize it.

III. CONCLUSION

Tendons play a fundamental role in transmitting loads from muscles to bones, allowing body movement, thanks to their hierarchical structure of collagen fibers. The discovery of auxetic behavior in tendons, particularly in the toe region, opens new possibilities for the design of artificial substitutes. By developing and optimizing a re-entrant unit cell, it is possible to reproduce the tendon's characteristic stress-strain response, controlling both the Poisson's ratio in the toe region and the stiffness in the linear strain region. Implementing these bio-inspired auxetic structures in artificial tendons could improve their mechanical performance, reduce the risk of failure, and bring them closer to the behavior of natural tendons.

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